

An Introduction to Ai & Machine Learning Investing

RebellionResearch.com :
“The Machine Learning Robo Advisor”

Alexander Fleiss - CEO

Why ML & AI?

- Ability to cover and calculate an amount data on a daily basis that is beyond human ability
- More accurately combine uncertain information
- Continuously learning to adapt to new market conditions

What is ML & AI?

- “A search through a vast maze of possibilities, a maze that describes the environment .” -Professor Herbert Simon of Carnegie Mellon, Father of Artificial Intelligence and 1978 Nobel Prize recipient
- “The art of creating machines that perform functions that require intelligence when performed by people.” -Ray Kurzweil, 1999 US National Medal of Technology recipient

Birth of ML & AI

- 1941, John Atanasoff and Clifford Berry invent the first electronic computer at Iowa State University
- 1956, MIT and Dartmouth Professors Minsky, Shannon and McCarthy invent Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence becomes powerful enough for Wall Street

- 1988, Professor Judea Pearl of UCLA introduced the use of probability and statistics to Artificial Intelligence

Wall Street Fundamental Data Becomes Accessible for Artificial Intelligence Investing

- 1998, Securities and Exchange Commission mandates that public companies electronically file corporate releases allowing for efficient processing of public filings
- 2005, Rebellion begins development of our Artificial Intelligence investment technology

What is the future of Artificial Intelligence investing?

- Sovereign & Corporate Debt
- Commodities
- Sector + Market Capitalization focused indexes
- Global Equity Markets

What makes Rebellion's AI unique?

- Flexible framework that can be adapted to different markets and economic conditions
- The ability to practice leading styles of investing: Value, Growth, Momentum and Macro

- Challenges with Longer Horizon investing
 - System constantly evolving
 - Market conditions constantly changing
 - Meanings of factors changes with time
 - High noise
 - System extremely complex. Many different factors contribute to stock returns.

AI For Short-term Trading

- Inefficiencies Exploited:
 - Human emotional and irrational decision-making
 - Market Making
- Large set of training data
- Easy to determine relevant factors
- Stable system

What is AI' s Value Add?

- The ability to dynamically and dispassionately shift economic and investment outlook
- Constantly learn how to manage its ever-increasing global daily data

AI Investing in Practice

- Inefficiencies Exploited:
 - Herd mentality
 - Improperly priced risk/reward characteristics
- Large set of factors chosen which correspond to different investment styles
 - Factors are stable
 - Contain a large amount of information

AI Investing in Practice

- Modified Bayesian learner to prevent over-fitting
 - Bayesian learners update probabilities given new pieces of information
 - Rate of learning can be controlled
 - Ensures the algorithm does not become too precise in predictions

AI Investing in Practice

- Overcoming the Bangladeshi Butter Problem
 - Each stock investment relies on average 30-40 factors
 - “Bad” factors expected to lead to market performance of the stock
 - The presence of several good factors still leads to expected outperformance

Inventors of our Ai

- Dr. Spencer Greenberg, PhD, Courant Math Institute of NYU and Bachelor's Degree in Applied Mathematics and Computer Science at Columbia University's Fu School of Engineering
- Jeremy Newton, won the American Chemistry regional award and placed 3rd in the American Computer Science League Tournament, defeated national chess champions and Bachelor's in Mathematics from Amherst College, Partner Thiel Capital

Inventors of our Ai

- Dr. Matthew Goldhirsh, Professor of Mathematics, Brooklyn College. Manager of New York State's Healthcare Analytics Team, PHD Applied Mathematics Columbia's University's Fu School of Engineering, Bachelor's from Cornell University

Ai' s Beta

- The Beta of the portfolio can be used as an expression of the Ai' s market prediction.
- Since 2007 Ai' s beta has been as high as 1.6 or an expected return of up to 60%
- Since 2007 Ai' s beta has been as low as .59 or an expected return of -41%

AI Beta Chart – Financial Crisis Case Study

QUESTIONS